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Faculty of Arts,
Federal University Gashua,
Yobe State, Nigeria

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JOURNAL INFORMATION

Bade Journal of Arts (BAJA) is a biannual peer-reviewed multidisciplinary journal of the Faculty of Arts, Federal University Gashua. It is a platform for the promotion of scholarship in the Arts.

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EDITORIAL

Research is the prime and the hub of the academia. Researches yield transformation of an unwholesome situation and drive transmogrification of human society. Needless to mention that all the products of human endeavours such as electricity and electrical appliances, beautiful and luxury edifices, fast and sophisticated means of transportation, medical facilities and curative drugs including other inventions in science and technology with ICT, come from researches in various areas. The ideation that initially begins as a flash is budded by research and then blossoms into a problem-solving phenomenon that brings an improvement in the quality of human life and the condition of other species of nature.

The above narrative underscores the need for research which is an essential part of the appointment of an academic staff of a university and why it is a major requirement for promotion from one rank to the other. And thus, the dictum: "publish or perish".

Bade Journal of Arts (BAJA) tripods on English, History and International Studies, and Islamic Studies which are the three programmes run in the Faculty of Arts, Federal University Gashua for now. The researches in these areas of arts published in the volume 2 of the faculty journal are engineered towards social transformation, national integration and national development. They focus on endemic socio-political and economic problems that tend to engage Nigerian developmental agenda on the reverse gear with the aim of jump-starting national development and national integration. These articles have workable findings that can take Nigeria out of the present predicaments and doldrums. The articles provide solutions to the social dilemma being experienced and offer strategies for the attainment of good social order. All the articles in this journal have humanity and national development as their goals.

On behalf of the Editorial Board of *BAJA* and members of the staff of the Faculty of Arts, Federal University Gashua, I will like to appreciate our colleagues in pen from other universities who have subscribed to this journal. The spatial diversity that your contributions accord the journal is priceless not only for cross-fertilisation of knowledge, but also national and international acceptability. We shall always look forward to publishing your ground-breaking researches. Our thanks are also due to our consulting editors for their scholarly advice and fellowship. Furthermore, members of the Editorial Board and members of the staff of the Faculty of Arts are hereby commended for their hard work and cooperation that birthed the faculty journal project. It is a dream come true and which would not have been realized if not for the cooperation and understanding of the management of FUGA led by our distinguished Vice Chancellor, Professor Maimuna Waziri.

Thank you all. Finally, I urge you to get a copy of *Bade Journal of Arts (BAJA)*, Volume 2, as a memento from the Faculty of Arts, Federal University Gashua, hosted by the Bade community and get another as another memento to someone else.

Dr Mohammed Attai Yakubu,
Editor-in-Chief *BAJA*,
(Pioneer Dean Faculty of Arts),
Deputy Vice Chancellor (Administration),
Federal University Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria.
June, 2024.

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Impacts of Globalisation on Africa's Educational System 1980-2000

Okolo, Abutu Lawrence PhD

Department of History and International Studies,
Federal University Gashua, Yobe State.

lauren4all2003@yahoo.com +2348035726309/+2348022454136

Nongonan, Apya Hyacinth PhD

Department of History and International Studies,
Federal University Gashua, Yobe State.

Fidelis, Imeje Ebri

Department of History and International Studies
Federal University Gashua, Yobe State.

and

Audu, Siyaka

Department of History and International Studies,
Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba, Kogi State.

Abstract

This study majorly investigates the impacts of globalisation on Africa's educational system. Despite the positive impacts of globalisation such as free movement of goods, services and capital which have resulted in economic growth and development, it has succeeded in dividing the world into blocs of developed and developing nations. To overcome the devastating effects that globalisation has on the African continent, science education, technological innovation, and industrial development should be prioritised by African governments; and supported by the developed world. Without ensuring this, the world economy will remain unjust to Africa as their resources are spent on consumption of commodities of industrialised countries. The sources of information are largely books, journals, library and internet materials. The findings here show weak cooperation among African countries to embrace globalisation and industrialisation but a balanced approach will require that African goods and services are equally consumed in the developed world. This is possible if the educational system is beforehand developed. It recommended that the government should employ more educational planners to plan the educational system in line with the demands of the global world using the latest technology.

Keywords: Africa, Education, Globalisation, Development, Inequalities

Introduction

Since ancient times, humans have sought distant places to settle, produce, and exchange goods enabled by improvements in technology and transportation. But not until the 19th century did global integration take off. Following centuries of European colonization and trade activity, that first "wave" of globalization was propelled by steamships, railroads, the telegraph, and other breakthroughs, and also by increasing economic cooperation among countries. The globalization trend eventually waned and crashed in the catastrophe of World War I, followed by post-war *protectionism*, the Great Depression, and World War II. After World War II in the mid-1940s, the United States led efforts to revive international trade and investment under negotiated ground rules, starting a second wave of globalization, which remains ongoing, though buffeted by periodic downturns and mounting political scrutiny. More so, after World War II, the United States helped build a global economic order governed by mutually accepted rules and overseen by multilateral institutions. The idea was to create a better world with countries seeking to cooperate with one another to promote prosperity and peace. Free trade and the rule of law were mainstays of the system, helping to prevent most economic disputes from escalating into larger conflicts (Peterson, 2018).

In another development, the term 'system' has respectively been defined by many scholars. System, according to Hall and Fegen, is a set of objects together with the relationship between the objects and their attributes (Hall and Fegen, 1956). While Griffith sees a system simply as a complex of elements in interaction (Griffiths, 1964). The systems approach therefore emphasizes that it is the whole, the combinations and relationship of parts that will provide the insight into the changes that occur in the course of interactions. The educational sector is a system within a larger system. Consequently, it must relate implicitly with its environment in order to realize its goals.

Education has been seen by many as the process of facilitating learning, knowledge, and a means through which skills are acquired. Fafunwa sees education as the aggregate of all the processes by which the child or young adults develop abilities, attributes and other forms of positive values to the society where they live (Fafunwa, 1974). Nevertheless, Abiodun assert that it is the proper nurturing, transmission and application of such knowledge that guarantees the development and sustenance of every society from day to day (Abiodun, 2012).

In another vein, globalization as a concept has been used in both positive and negative way by different people in different situations. Everyone looks at the concept from his or her point of view and interests. However, there is an agreement among all theorists that globalization has had enormous impact on societies at economic, political, and cultural levels. From the literature on globalisation, it seems like everything is globalising in this world as a result of the transformation of the world to a small village, a global village. This means borders are not any longer insurmountable barriers to any kind of connections and integration between nations. It is argued in the literature that such impact of globalisation reaches both

developing and developed nations. All of their governmental systems are believed to be affected by the various processes of globalisation (Khalaf, 2011).

Regarding the linkages between globalisation and education, much has been written in recent years examining how education has been affected. For example, Marginson (1999) stated that education "has become a primary medium of globalisation and an incubator of its agents". Additionally, Priestly (2002) argues that national education systems have been changed quite noticeably by the processes of globalisation and that most changes happening recently in education can be attributed to the effects of and responses to globalisation. Correspondingly, Jones and Coleman (2005) state that no education system globally can survive and stay unaffected by globalisation.

This study examines the effects of globalisation on education in Africa, in relation to the technologies of the new century that have changed the entire world ostensibly positively, as well as, the inequalities in the use of internet created by pressures and pulls of globalisation in destabilising the nation state. The shattering outcome of globalisation pressures and flows on African economy and the consequences on education, the socio-economic and educational disparities and inequities that constitute injustice, reduction of human dignity, are also highlighted. Western education in Africa was initiated by the missionaries mostly during the colonial period and shortly after independence. The agitation by Africans to provide mass education for their people at all levels has met with challenges, some of which will be discussed in this article. More importantly, autonomous African universities at inception in the 1960s expanded as a result of local and international supports. Inter-linkages were forged with United States Agency for International Development (USAID), Rockefeller and Ford Foundations, Carnegie Corporation and UNESCO and they all made commitments to help African universities and colleges. There were interactions in various areas of academics - staff exchange, regular annual conferences and fellowships tenable in the United Kingdom and United States of America for the conduct of research. African participation intensified and twenty-six other members that included Botswana, Lesotho, Swaziland, Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, Nigeria Liberia, etc. were involved (Fafunwa, 1991). African universities then, were of international repute. The pressures of globalisation brought drastic changes to all this.

Finally, the focus of this paper is to investigate how globalisation has reshaped the terrain of education in Africa. In order to make it clear, the paper will start by clarifying the concept of globalisation, and consider its nature. Then, sub-Saharan Africa's experience in the era of globalisation will be uncovered by pointing out the main difference in the use of internet facilities globally and its effects on education.

The Concept of Globalisation

According to Melina Kolb (2021), globalisation is the word used to describe the increasing interdependence of the world's economies, cultures, and populations,

brought about by cross-border trade in goods and services, technology, and flows of investment, people, and information. Countries have built economic partnerships to facilitate these movements over many centuries. But the term gained popularity after the Cold War in the early 1990s, as these cooperative arrangements shaped modern everyday life. Shenka and Luo defined globalisation as the growing economic interdependencies of countries worldwide through the increasing volume and variety of cross-border transactions in goods and services and of international capital flows, as well as through the paid and widespread diffusion of technology and information (Shenka and Luo, 2004). Its features include integration, change and interaction. Oluabunwa opined that globalisation can be seen as an evolution which is systematically restructuring interactive phases among nations by breaking down barriers in the areas of culture, commerce, communication and several other fields of endeavour (Oluabunwa, 1999).

Similarly, globalisation on the surface looks good given that the technological innovations of the 21st century have seemingly reduced the whole world to a global village, because of the flow of trade and investments, the ease of travel, ease with which we can see and hear news and most extraordinarily, the internet which gives virtually limitless access to store of knowledge. Globalisation has affected every sphere of society and human living and so has been defined by writers in various ways in relation to its impact on education in Africa. It is the growing integration of economy and society around the world. It has become the concept with which huge economic, political, cultural changes that characterise human society at the turn of the 21st century is interpreted (Okoli, 2012).

Furthermore, Okoli and Khor agree that in the process of globalisation, investment resources; growth and modern technology are focused in a few countries (mainly in North America, Europe, Japan and East Asian newly industrialising countries (NICs) (Okoli, 2012; Khor, 2001). The Human Development Report of 1996 showed that over the past three decades, only 15 countries have enjoyed high growth while 89 countries were worse off economically than they were 10 or more years earlier. Economic gains have greatly benefited a few countries at the expense of many, according to the report. The accelerated pace of technological development has made access to knowledge a requirement for participation in the global economy. The impact of the new information and communication technology (ICT) has significantly changed the speed of production, use and distribution of knowledge economy depending on how much it can generate and share knowledge. These concepts of globalisation and more will be applied in this study accordingly.

According to World Health Organisation, globalisation can be defined as "the increased interconnectedness and interdependence of peoples and countries. It is generally understood to include two inter-related elements: the opening of international borders to increasingly fast flows of goods, services, finance, people and ideas; and the changes in institutions and policies at national and international levels that facilitate or promote such flows" (Youmatter, 2019).

Globalisation is the process of interaction and integration among people, companies, and governments worldwide. Globalisation has accelerated since the 18th century due to advances in transportation and communication technology. This increase in global interactions has caused a growth in international trade and the exchange of ideas, beliefs, and culture. Globalisation is primarily an economic process of interaction and integration that is associated with social and cultural aspects. However, disputes and diplomacy are also large parts of the history of globalisation, and of modern globalisation (Albrow and King, 1990).

Economically, globalisation involves goods, services, data, technology, and the economic resources of capital. The expansion of global markets liberalises the economic activities of the exchange of goods and funds. Removal of cross-border trade barriers has made the formation of global markets more feasible. Advances in transportation, like the steam locomotive, steamship, jet engine, and container ships, and developments in telecommunication infrastructure, like the telegraph, Internet, and mobile phones, have been major factors in globalisation and have generated further interdependence of economic and cultural activities around the globe (Stever, 1972).

Globalisation supports new job opportunities but also contributes to job displacement. It does not significantly change the total number of positions in the economy, as job numbers are primarily driven by business cycles and Federal Reserve and fiscal policies. Nevertheless, Peterson Institute study finds 156,250 US manufacturing jobs were lost on net each year between 2001 and 2016 from expanded trade in manufactured goods, which represents less than 1 percent of the workers laid off in a typical year. Low-wage workers in certain regions are most affected. Many of them also face lower earnings or have dropped out of the workforce. Bigger factors than trade that have driven job displacements are labour-saving technologies, like automated machines and artificial intelligence. Better-paying positions have opened up in manufactured exports-especially in high-tech areas, such as computers, chemicals, and transportation equipment-and other high-skill work, notably in business services, such as finance and real estate (Peterson Institute for International Economics, 2021).

From the above definitions and explanations given by scholars, we can see that the features of globalisation include integration, change and interaction. Informed by the above features and elements of globalisation, we can now provide a definition that will guide us through this paper. Globalisation could be seen as the process of integration and interaction between diverse groups, governments, systems and nations. It is principally aimed at the homogenisation of various social, economic and political development sectors of the globe. Globalisation in the past was greatly aided by trade. But presently, globalisation has been to a very large extent aided by information technology. Globalisation has impacts on the environment, culture, human being, political, cultural and economic development. Similarly, *globalization* is the word used to describe the growing interdependence of the world's economies, cultures, and populations, brought about by cross-border

trade in goods and services, technology, and flows of investment, people, and information. Countries have built economic partnerships to facilitate these movements over many centuries.

Sub-Saharan Africa's Experience in the Era of Globalisation

Sub-Saharan Africa is one of the poorest regions in the world with 33 of the least developed countries. Until now Sub-Saharan Africa has never fully managed to escape the sufferings from its former historical experience. The most important factor for SSA's poor development is its history, specifically Africa's colonial period and the following post-colonial period. The colonialisation of Africa began when European traders established the "Triangular Trade" in the Early Modern age. The Triangular Trade included three regions involved in the trading route: Europe, Africa and America. The Europeans established a great slavery network in Africa from which slaves were then traded to America (Sahn and Younger, 2009).

For Waters (2001), globalisation is mainly a phenomenon of capital mobility which involves direct foreign investment and international portfolio flows. As a result, transnational companies and financial institutions, operating independently of national boundaries and domestic economic considerations, dominate a global economy. For Fafowora (1999), globalisation seeks to make itself present worldwide at the world stage or global arena. It deals with the increasing breakdown of trade barriers and the increasing integration of world markets. Globalisation is an evolving process, systematically restructuring interactive phases among nations by breaking down barriers in the areas of culture, commerce, communication and several other trends of endeavour. This is apparent from its promotion of free market economies, liberal democracy, good governance, gender equality and environmental sustainability among other holistic values for the people of the member states.

Furthermore, the Europeans extended it to a shocking number, this eventually led to wars and conflicts in Africa. Africa continued to be closely linked to Europe up to the period between World War II and 1980. In this so called "age of decolonization" European colonies struggled to gradually achieve political independence. Unfortunately, problems came about which were implemented by the Europeans. During the colonialisation, many modern SSA borders were defined without any heedfulness for indigenous cultures which created civil conflicts between the various groups. The Europeans deliberately did this to minimize the chance of resistance of the indigenous people. After European colonies in Africa became independent, they were left with many challenges facing economic development. Africa was and still is known for its richness in raw materials and Europe took advantage of it because these materials were designated as low-priced exports for the European market. Every step in the direction of industrialisation was neglected and, in that way, Africa had no chance to develop itself. After the decolonisation, many African countries' governments became dictatorships which also worked against the development of the continent. This did not change until the

end of the Cold War. Only then a few African nations, such as Botswana, the Gambia and Mauritius, were able to establish a democratic ruling system. However, most African nations are still struggling to enjoy the same freedom and welfare as Western countries do (Essential Humanities, 2013; Karner, 2018).

Ibrahim and Karner opined that Africa's, position in the international system has been considerably weakened by the fact that it has been losing the race for economic development in general, and human development in particular, to other regions, these poor performances by African countries accounts in part for the political and social instability and rise of authoritarian regimes that have characterized much of postcolonial Africa, further weakening the ability of African countries to deal effectively with globalisation (Ibrahim, 2023; Karner 2018).

For Waters (2001), globalisation is mainly a phenomenon of capital mobility which involves direct foreign investment and international portfolio flows. As a result, transnational companies and financial institutions, operating independently of national boundaries and domestic economic considerations, dominate a global economy. For Fafowora (1999), globalisation seeks to make itself present worldwide at the world stage or global arena. It deals with the increasing breakdown of trade barriers and the increasing integration of world markets. Globalisation is an evolving process, systematically restructuring interactive phases among nations by breaking down barriers in the areas of culture, commerce, communication and several other trends of endeavour. This is apparent from its promotion of free market economies, liberal democracy, good governance, gender equality and environmental sustainability among other holistic values for the people of the member states.

Between 1970 and 2000, real income growth failed to keep pace with population growth in SSA. After posting a modest average annual growth rate in real per capita income of about 0.7 per cent during the 1970s, these rates turned negative during the 1980s and 1990s, falling 1 per cent and 0.5 per cent, respectively. Since 2000, SSA countries have posted improved growth rates, largely thanks to primary commodity-driven recoveries, and most seem to have recovered relatively quickly from the global economic crisis. Even so, average real per capita income is still barely higher than in 1970 and SSA fell behind all other regions on most development indicators (see table 1). The regional average also conceals vast differences within the continent, where countries affected by conflict and political instability were the worst performers, and mainly resource-rich countries have profited from the commodities boom since 2000. Furthermore, the weak and often erratic growth performances have been accompanied by regressive trends in income distribution in many countries, with a particularly marked drop in the average per capita income of the poorest 20 per cent in SSA.

Table 1. Average annual per capita growth rates, 1960-2008

	1960-1969	1970-1979	1980-1989	1990-1999	2000-2008
World	3.4	2.1	1.4	1.2	1.7
East Asia and the Pacific	1.3	4.4	6.1	7.1	8.0
Europe and Central Asia				-2.0	5.8
Latin America and the Caribbean	2.4	3.1	0.8	1.5	2.3
Middle East and North Africa		2.8	0.4	1.8	2.7
South Asia	1.8	0.3	3.2	3.3	5.4
Sub-Saharan Africa	2.0	0.7	-1.0	-0.5	2.4
GDP per capita in constant 2000 US dollars					
World	2 806	3 659	4 177	4 780	5 585
East Asia and the Pacific	140	210	358	696	1299
Europe and Central Asia			2 296	1 847	2 496
Latin America and the Caribbean	2 277	3 099	3 446	3 643	4 197
Middle East and North Africa	932	1 295	1 372	1 464	1 687
South Asia	201	224	274	373	545
Sub-Saharan Africa	475	577	552	504	553

Source: (World Bank, 2005, p. 274; Jomo Kwame et al, 2011).

Not only is this likely to undermine human resource development and social as well as political cohesion in SSA, it is also likely to restrict future growth prospects.

In historical perspective, this development failure was unexpected and seems a lot less unavoidable than the longstanding "Afro-pessimistic" discourse on Africa's economic development would have us believe. In the 1960s, per capita gross domestic product (GDP) and GDP growth were higher in Africa than in Asia, and expectations then were that African countries would grow faster due to their superior resource endowments (World Bank, 2005; Jomo Kwame et al, 2011). However, they failed to adjust to changing global economic conditions and went on to experience over two lost decades of development from the late 1970s until the early 2000s.

Difference in the Use of Internet Facilities Globally and its Effects on Education

Nkechi J. Okoli (2012) had aptly pointed out that the greatest destabilising influence on the sovereignty of the nation is the global economy. The globalisation pressure has led to the erosion of national sovereignty and nation borders leaving the nation with little political and policy room for action. It struggles to maintain international competitiveness of its nation economy. This destabilisation has given rise to the emergence of few multinational corporations that dominate the use of internet. It is true that countries could benefit from knowledge economy depending on how much they can generate and share knowledge. Yet looking at the involvement of corporations in globalisation of economy, they are located within the boundaries of a handful of developed nations. The International Labour Organization (ILO) in 2001 explained that new technologies can have impact on countries no matter their level of economic development. Transition countries like China, Costa Rica, Malaysia, Singapore and Romania have successfully created, with the help of relative effective education systems, information technology niches that make it possible for them to compete at the global market, since the new micro-economics stress a highly skilled flexible workforce to national success within the new global knowledge economy, yet it has grown digital gap among nations. Disparities in per capita income and standards of living have emerged resulting from the pressures and pulls of globalisation on countries globally, thereby dividing countries according to their ability to use, adapt, produce and diffuse knowledge. Thus, it places the developed world on a class of their own while the Third World countries stand marginalized in the global outfit as shown in Table 1.

Table 2: Random sampling in the use of Internet in various countries in 2000

Country	Number of Personal Computers per 1000 inhabitant	Number of Households connected with Internet	Number of Internet Users per 5,000 of the Population
South Korea		3, 000, 000	
Japan		450, 000	
Burkina Faso	1		0.05
South Africa	27		
Chile	38		
Singapore	172		
Switzerland	348		
Sub- Saharan African Countries			1
Europe & North America			800

Sources: Adapted from The International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank, 2002; Nkechi J. Okoli 2012.

Table 2 shows that Burkina Faso has less than one computer per 1000 inhabitants compared to one computer to 172 and 348 inhabitants in Singapore and Switzerland respectively. In Sub-Saharan Africa there exists one internet user per 5,000 inhabitants while in Korea and Japan, 3,000,000 and 450,000 households respectively, are connected to internet. Africa is highly marginalized. It reduces their chances of participation in the global knowledge economy.

Nkechi J. Okoli (2012) asserts that the pulls and pressures of globalisation have affected educational policies. Education is universally acclaimed as the key to sustainable development and advancement of human welfare. To African nations, education is the key not only to socio-economic development and political stability, but also the instrument to translate the nations from league of low to those of high-level technology nations. Colonial education was not geared towards popular or mass education of the African. After the Second World War Africa's demand for education increased and at independence channelled huge percentage of their budgets to education based on the economist's modernisation theory which focused on the productive capacity of human manpower in the development process. In so doing, they treated the improvement of the human workforce as a form of capitalist investment. Thus, the human capitalist theory postulates that the most efficient path to the national development of any society lies in the improvement of its population, that is, its human capital. Education was not to be viewed simply as a

form of consumption but rather as a productive investment. He argued that education does not only improve the individual choices available to men, but an educated population provides the type of labour force necessary for industrial development and economic growth. (Schultz in: Fagerlind and Saha, 1989; 19; Nkechi Okoli 2012; 5). The humanist theory provided basic justification for large public expenditure on education in both developed and developing countries. The theory was consistent with the ideologies of democracy and liberal progressivism found in most Western societies. The theory's appeal was based on the presumed economic return of investment in education both at the macro and micro levels. For politicians and decision makers, efforts to promote investment in human capital were seen to result in rapid economic growth for society. For the individuals, such investment was seen to provide returns in form of individual economic success and achievement (Karabel and Halsey, 1977; Blaug, 1976; Nkechi J. Okoli, 2012). Leaders of 33 African nations met in Addis Ababa in 1961. The most widely discussed aspects of the final report were the short- and long-term goals which estimated the future educational targets of the continent. The short-term plan looked into the urgent production of intermediate and high-level manpower to man the institution of the states while the long-term was to raise the ratios of the three levels of education. Table III shows that ratios of elementary schools, secondary schools and universities were to be raised from 40.0:3.0:0.2 in 1961 to 100.0:23.0:2.0 by 1980. This meant that only 40% of primary school age children in Africa were actually enrolled in 1961 and that by 1980, 100%, that is all children of primary school age would be in school. The conference projected and advocated for universal primary education by 1980 all over Africa.

Table 3: Long-Term Plan (1961-80): Enrolment and Equivalent Percentages of the Three Levels of Education

Educational Level	1961-62	1965-66 Enrolments	1970-71 (in thousand)	1980-81
Primary	11,586.0	15,586.0	20,378.0	32,808.0
Secondary	903.7	1,833.5	3,900.0	5,905.4
Higher	25.5	30.3	55.0	328.8
	Percentage	Of	group	Enrolled
		level/age		
Primary	40.0	51.0	71.0	100
Secondary	30.0	9.0	15.0	23.0

Source: Final Report of Conference of African Heads of State on the Development of Education in Africa (UNESCO: 1961; Nkechi J. Okoli, 2012).

The universal primary education scheme was floated by many African governments in the middle of the 1970s. By 1980s the scheme had broken down and parents started paying school fees for their children. Despite the Jomtien EFA declaration, by 1998 only 42% of African primary children were out of school and by 2000, 39% were still out of school. Africa may never meet the 2015 deadline. Unfortunately, the pressure and pulls of globalisation brought to bear on the entire education system in Africa. Policies were affected. With the global economic framework education is now regarded as the policy key to the future prosperity of nations (Brown et al., 1997 in Henry et al., 2008). The new human capital theory focuses on micro-economics which stress a high skilled and flexible work force to national success within the new global knowledge economy. Education by global standards is seen as a social good which justified increased funding. Students are now asked by institutions to pay all kinds of fees. Only few can pay. Globally education is deemed important for the competitive advantage of nations. The commitment and capacity of governments to fund it has been weakened. Thus, education institutions have financial constraints and this has affected the quality, quantity and performance (Okoli, 2012; Ibrahim, 2013).

Conclusion

Globalisation is presently at the centre of debates about development. For its proponents, it promises the potential for new levels of economic development and cooperation and a means to end poverty among the teeming youths. For its critics, it increases the disparity in power and wealth between North and South and accelerates and deepens poverty and social exclusion. These arguments have profound implications for education systems and providers, and for those 'receiving' education. Education is seen as a key resource in benefiting from globalisation through improved competitiveness and better connectivity to the information super-highway. It is seen as a way of reducing the 'digital divide' and processes of exclusion. Education is also deeply affected by the processes associated with globalisation. New sources of information and new technologies to support learning are emerging yet the disparities are apparent. New skills for internet literacy are being identified for schools and universities to deliver on. Globalisation also challenges the notion of a national education system and a national curriculum, furthering the growth of 'international schools', distance learning and global recruitment by Northern providers. Finally, inequality, marginalisation, and pauperisation. Millions of people in the sub-Saharan Africa (most especially the females) cannot go to school because they are living in abject poverty while a few have the chance. Globalisation as a phenomenon promotes education and economic growth but its pulls and pressures have created injustice, inequality and inequities that reduce human dignity to the barest minimum.

This research recommends a rethinking of globalisation. It should be made to serve all the people both in the developed and developing nations and aggressive pursuit of educational empowerment of the females especially is recommended.

More so, African continent and the developed economies should work in tandem and commit resources and energies to harnessing the capacity of the African poor for their development. It is hoped that the global actors will realise that it is not beneficial to them or to anyone else to play globalisation-game without the poor. For globalisation to ultimately be beneficial to everyone-the rich and the poor-all must have certain levels of capacity that permit them to effectively participate in the game.

The contemporary world, where resources and benefits are concentrated in the hands of very few, is not a comfortable world for anybody. And to sustain it is to breed future insecurity as most of the poor strives to get a share of the riches concentrated in the hands of the few. It is clear that globalisation benefits those who have the capacity to harness it but can be very detrimental to those whom it finds not prepared. Most African States are not prepared, especially in terms of having the requisite capacity.

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